

DIVERSITY OF INSECTA: ORTHOPTERA OF KANCHIPURAM DISTRICT IN TAMIL NADU

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ABSTRACT

The Order Orthoptera includes short horned and long horned grasshoppers, crickets and grouse locusts. These insects range from sizes less than 5 mm to 115 mm. They are distributed worldwide and mainly in warmer regions and are in the temperate zone. They are found in all terrestrial habitats from subterranean burrows and caves to tree tops, and from dense forest to savanna and deserts. Most of them are phytophagous. The order Orthoptera is one of the largest having over 20,000 species worldwide with about 10% of the total world species (1,750 species) recorded from India (Hirdesh Kumar and Mohd. Kamil Usmani, 2014). The paper presents the checklist and diagnostic characters of orthoptera of Kanchipuram district along with their known distribution which includes 12 species/subspecies of belonging to 9 genera under 2 Suborder, 3 Superfamilies, 3 families and 7 subfamilies.

Key words: Orthoptera, Grasshopper diversity, Kanchipuram district, Eastern Ghats.

INTRODUCTION

Kanchipuram district is situated on the North East coast of Tamil Nadu. It is bound by Bay of Bengal in the East, Vellore and Thiruvannamalai districts in the west, Thiruvallur and Chennai districts in the north, and Villuppuram district in the south. It lies between 11° 00' to 12° 00' latitudes and 77° 28' to 78° 50' longitudes. The district has a total geographical area of 4, 43,210 hectares and a coastline of 57 km. The pre-

monsoon rainfall is almost uniform throughout the district. The coastal regions receive more rainfall than the interior ones. The district is mainly dependent on the monsoon rains. Failure of monsoon leads to distress condition. Northeast and Southwest monsoon are the major donors, with 54% and 36% contribution each to the total annual rainfall. During normal monsoon, the district receives a rainfall of 1200 mm. The Palaru River is the most important river running through the district. Through most of the year it remains dry, attributed to the construction of dams across the river in Andhra Pradesh. There are only a few hills of considerable elevation in the district. The southern part of Maduranthakam taluk contains small hills. The total forest area in the district is 23,586 hectares. Agriculture forms the primary occupation of the people with 47 percent of the population of this district are engaged in it. Paddy is the major crop cultivated in this district

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and the other major crops grown in the district of Kanchipuram include groundnut, sugarcane, cereals and millets and pulses. Insects are prevailing as a dominant faunal population of this district. In this context an effort has been made to measure the diversity of orthoptera among those insects.

The Order Orthoptera includes short horned and long horned grasshoppers, crickets and grouse locusts. These insects range from sizes less than 5 mm to 115 mm. They are distributed worldwide and mainly in warmer regions and are in the temperate zone. They are found in all terrestrial habitats from subterranean burrows and caves to tree tops, and from dense forest to savanna and deserts. Most of them are phytophagous. These insects are of much economic importance as many species are serious pests of crops, forests and pastures. The antennae are filiform but in some they are ensiform. Tarsi 2 to 4 segmented; hind femora enlarged and modified for jumping. Wings fully developed or brachypterous or not present. Fore wings are generally in the form of leathery tegmina, hind wings membranous and fan like. The female has external long or short ovipositor. Male of most species stridulate and female generally do not produce sound.

The order Orthoptera is one of the largest having over 20,000 species worldwide with about 10% of the total world species (1,750 species) recorded from India (Hirdesh Kumar and Mohd. Kamil Usmani, 2014).

Many authors like Bolivar (1900, 1902), Chitra, Soundararajan and Gunathilagaraj (2000, 2001), Chopard (1935, 1969), Fletcher (1914, 1921), Ghosh (1996), Hancock (1915), Hebard (1929), Henry (1937, 1940), Ingrisch and Muralirangan (2003), Kandeban, Raguraman and Ganapathy (2004), Kandeban, Raguraman, Ganapathy and Gunathilagaraj (2004), Karpakakunjaram, Kolatkar and Muralirangan (2002), Kesavaram (1986), Kevan (1952), Kevan and Singh (1964), Kirby (1914), Muralirangan and Ananthakrishnan (1974), Muralirangan, Shrinivasan and Suresh (1992), Prabakar (2009), Shishodia and Kulkarni

(2001), HA Dhamke et al (2014), Shrinivasan (1986), TV Sathe et al (2014), Prabakar D (2014) Shrinivasan and Muralirangan (1992) had studied the orthoptera fauna of Tamil Nadu earlier. This communication is based on the faunistic surveys undertaken by Ms. D. Vimala recently in Kanchipuram district of Tamil Nadu. The present study is represented by 12 species. A systematic account of the same is presented below:

SYSTEMATIC LIST

Order **ORTHOPTERA**

Suborder **CAELIFERA**

Infraorder **ACRIDIDEA**

Superfamily group **ACRIDOMORPHA**

Superfamily **PYRGOMORPHOIDEA** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1882

Family **PYRGOMORPHIDAE** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1882

Subfamily **PYRGOMORPHINAE** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1882

Tribe **Atractomorphini** Bolívar, 1905

1. *Atractomorpha crenulata crenulata* (Fabricius, 1793) Image: Plat 1

Tribe **Pyrgomorphini** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1882

Subtribe **Pyrgomorphina** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1882

Genus **Pyrgomorpha** Serville, 1838

Subgenus *Pyrgomorpha* Serville, 1838

Species *conica* (Olivier, 1791)

2. *Pyrgomorpha (Pyrgomorpha) conicaconica* (Olivier, 1791)

Subfamily **ORTHACRIDINAE** Bolívar, 1905

Tribe **Orthacridini** Bolívar, 1905

Genus group **Orthacris**

Genus **Neorthacris** Kevan & Singh, 1964

3. *Neorthacris simulans* (Bolivar, 1902) Image: Plate 1

Superfamily **ACRIDOIDEA** MacLeay, 1821

Family **ACRIDIDAE** MacLeay, 1821

Subfamily **ACRIDINAE** MacLeay, 1821

Tribe **Acridini** MacLeay, 1821

Figure-1. Systematic list of Orthoptera of Kanchipuram district in Tamil Nadu.

Crenulata crenulata (Fabricius, 1793)

Neorthacris simulans (Bolivar, 1902)

Acrida gigantea (Herbst, 1794)

Aiolopus thalassinus tamulus (Fabricius, 1798)

Eyrepcnemis alacris alacris (Serville, 1839)

Gryllotalpa africana africana Palisot de Beauvois, 1805

Genus *Acrida* Linnaeus, 1758

4. *Acrida exaltata* (Walker, 1859)
5. *Acrida gigantea* (Herbst, 1794) Image: Plate 1
6. *Acrida turrita* (Linnaeus, 1758)
Subfamily **OEDIPODINAE** Walker, 1871

Tribe **Epacromiini** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893.

Genus *Aiolopus* Fieber, 1853

7. *Aiolopus simulatrix simulatrix* (Walker, 1870)

8. *Aiolopus thalassinus tamulus* (Fabricius, 1798) Image: Plate 1
Tribe **Trilophidiini** Shumakov, 1963
Genus **Trilophidia** Stål, 1873
9. *Trilophidia annulata* (Thunberg, 1815)
Subfamily **OXYINAE** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893
Tribe **Oxyini** Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893
Genus *Oxya* Serville, 1831
10. *Oxya fuscovittata* (Marschall, 1836)
Subfamily **EYPREPOCNEMIDINAE** Brunner Von Wattenwyl, 1893
Tribe **Eyprepopcnemidini** Brunner Von Wattenwyl, 1893
Genus *Eyprepopcnemis* Fieber, 1853
11. *Eyprepopcnemis alacris alacris* (Serville, 1839) Image: Plate 1
Suborder **ENSIFERA**
Superfamily **GRYLLOIDEA** Laicharting, 1781
Family **GRYLLOTALPIDAE** Leach, 1815
Subfamily **GRYLLOTALPINAE** Leach, 1815
Genus *Gryllotalpa* Latreille, 1802
Subspecies **africana**
12. *Gryllotalpa africana africana* Palisot de Beauvois, 1805 Image: Plate 1

SYSTEMATIC ACCOUNT

1. *Atractomorpha crenulata crenulata*

(Fabricius, 1793)

1793. *Truxalis crenulatus*, Fabricius, *Ent. Syst.*, ii, p. 28.
1815. *Truxalis scaber*, Thunberg, *Mem. Acad. Sci. St. Petersb.*, **5**: 266.
1842. *Acridium psittacium*, De Haan, pt., Temminck, *Verhandel., Orth.*, p.149, pl. xxiii, fig. 1 (nec p. 146).
1859. *Truxalis porrecta*, Walker, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, **4**(3): 222.
1861. *Atractomorpha consobrina*, Saussure, *Ann. Soc. Ent. France*, (4) I, p. 475.
1905. *Atractomorpha crenulata*, var. *prasina*, Bolivar, *Bol. Soc. Espan. Hist. Nat.* v, pp.197, 201.
1918. *Atractomorpha obscura*, Bolivar, *Rev. Acad. Cienc. Madr.*, **16** : 392.
1960. *Atractomorpha crenulata*, Banerjee & Kevan, *Treubia*, **25**: 166.

1963. *Pygomorpha acuminipennis*, Blanchard, *Ark. Zool.*, **16**: 79.

1969. *Atractomorpha crenulata*, Keven & Chen., *Zool. J. Linn. Soc.*, **48**: 187.

2009. *Atractomorpha crenulatacrenulata*, Prabakar, *Fauna of Tamil Nadu, State Fauna Series*, **17**, Part 1, *Zool. Surv. India*: 47.

Materials Examined:

2exs., 1 Male and 1 Female; India: Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, Vedal; 14. viii. 2014, Coll.: D. Vimala & Party.

Diagnostic characters:

Body slender, green, pubescent. Antennae short and stout. Pronotum punctured and sparingly granulated. Head and pronotum with the sides slightly sloping, crenulated behind the eyes, the crenulation often pink. Prosternum with an obtusely rounded tubercle. Tegmina pointed, extending for one-fourth of their length beyond the hind femora; wings shorter than the tegmina.

Distribution:

India : Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Gujarat, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Jharkhand, Karnataka, Kerala, Lakshadweep Islands, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal. **Elsewhere:** Bangladesh, Cambodia, Laos, Maldive Island, Malaya, Myanmar, Nepal, Pakistan, South Vietnam, Sri Lanka, Sumatra and Thailand.

Remarks: It is a pest of Paddy.

2. *Pygomorpha (Pygomorpha) conicaconica* (Olivier, 1791)

1791. *Acrydium conicum* Olivier, *Encyclopédie Méthodique* **6**: 230.

1914. *Pygomorpha conica* Kirby, *Fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma*. Orthoptera (Acrididae) 175.

1966. *Acridium conicum* Dirsh, *Publ. Cult. Comp. Diamant. Angola Ser.* **3**, Vol. 74:83.

2008. *Pyrgomorphaconica*

Usmani, *Zootaxa* **1946**:16.

2009. *Pyrgomorphaconica* Hemp, *Jour. Orth.*

Res. **18**(2):194.

Materials Examined:

1 ex., Male; India: Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, Kalpattu; 17. viii. 2014, Coll.: D. Vimala & Party.

Diagnostic characters:

Grey with a whitish line running below the eyes which is bordering the deflexed lobes beneath. Fastigium of the vertex longer than broad; antennae stout, blackish, shorter than the head and pronotum together; median carina distinct from the fastigium over the head and pronotum; lateral carinae incomplete. Surface of pronotum finely granulate, hind border rounded, hind sulcus placed much behind the middle. Tegmina grey; wings hyaline. Hind tibiae above with no outer apical spine. Metasternal lobes produced behind the foveolae and contiguous; abdomen spotted with black above.

Distribution:

India: Madhya Pradesh and Tamil Nadu.

Remarks: It is a pest of Paddy.

3. *Neorthacris simulans* (Bolivar, 1902)

1902. *Orthacris simulans* Bolívar, *Ann. Soc. ent. Fr.* **70**:608,611.

1910. *Orthacris simulans* Kirby, *A Synonymic Catalogue of Orthoptera* (Orthoptera Saltatoria, Locustidae vel Acridiidae) **3**(2):336.

1975. *Orthacris simulans* Vasantharaj & Kumaraswami, *Elements Econ. Ent. Madras*.

1977. *Orthacris simulans* Kevan, In Beier [Ed.], *Orthopterorum Catalogus* **16**:83.

Materials Examined:

1 ex., Female; India: Tamil Nadu; Kanchipuram district, Vedal; 14. viii. 2014, Coll.: D. Vimala & Party.

Diagnostic characters:

Closely allied to the last species, but with a large abdominal tympanum. The male has the side of the head and thorax and the lateral lobes of the pronotum dull reddish and there are a few white tubercles on the head. The last segment of the abdomen in the male is deeply sinuated, with the two lobes turning outwards, the supra-anal lamina carinated in the middle, and the cerci incurved at the tip.

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu.

Remarks: It is a pest of Paddy.

Superfamily **ACRIDOIDEA** MacLeay, 1821

Family **ACRIDIDAE** MacLeay, 1821

Subfamily **ACRIDINAE** MacLeay, 1821

Tribe **Acridini** MacLeay, 1821

Genus *Acrida* Linnaeus, 1758

4. *Acrida exaltata* (Walker, 1859)

1859. *Truxalis exaltata*, Walker, *Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist.*, **4**(3): 222

1893. *Truxalis brevicollis*, Bolivar, *Feuille Jeunes. Nat.*, xxiii, pp.162, 164.

1902. *Acrida lugubris*, Burr, *Trans. Ent. Soc. Lond.* pp. 157, 170.

1914. *Acrida exaltata*, Kirby, *Fauna of British India*: Vol. I (Acrididae):99.

1914. *Acrida lugubris*, Kirby, *Fauna of British India*: Vol. I (Acrididae):99.

1936. *Acrida curta*, Uvarov, *Zool. J. Linn. Soc.*, **39**: 536.

1954. *Acrida exaltata*, Dirsh, *Bull. Soc. Faud. Ent.*, **38**: 149.

1956. *Acrida lugubris astigmata*, Prasad, *Proc. Nation. Acad. Sci. India*, **1**: 22.

2009. *Acrida exaltata*, Prabakar, *Fauna of Tamil Nadu, State Fauna Series*, **17**, Part 1, *Zool. Surv. India*: 46.

Materials Examined:

2 exs., 1 Male and 1 Female; India: Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, Kalpattu, 17. viii. 2014, Coll.: D. Vimala & Party. 2 exs., 1 Male and 1 Female; India: Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, Arcot, 19. viii. 2014, Coll.: D. Vimala & Party.

Diagnostic characters:

Body green in colour; fastigium of vertex broad, laminate and truncate at extremity; head conically ascending, basal part narrow and as long as the pronotum; pronotal disc weakly tectiform; transverse sulcus of pronotum placed near the middle of disc; tegmina without pointed apex, a little produced beyond the hind knees; wings slightly shorter than tegmina and yellowish hyaline in colour; the cells in the posterior part of the wings are cloudy in the middle; hind femora is smaller than tegmina; the male subgenital plate is long.

Distribution:

India : Andaman & Nicobar Islands, Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Gujarat, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal. **Elsewhere:** Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Iran, Pakistan, Saudi Arabia, South East Tibet, Sri Lanka, Yemen and West Aden.

Remarks: It is a pest of Paddy.

5. *Acrida gigantea* (Herbst, 1794)

1786. *Truxalis giganteus* Herbst, *Archiv der Insectengeschichte. Herausgegeben von Johan Caspar Fuessly* 7-8:191.

1790. *Gryllus (Acrida) giganteus* Gmelin, *Caroli a Linné Systema Naturae* 1(4):2057.

1869. *Truxalis giganteus* Scudder, *Smithson. misc. Coll.* 8:83.

1910. *Acrida gigantea* Kirby, *A Synonymic Catalogue of Orthoptera (Orthoptera Saltatoria, Locustidae vel Acridiidae)* 3(2):93.

2012. *Acrida gigantea* Nayeem & Usmani, *Munis Entomology & Zoology* 7(1):404.

Materials Examined:

2 exs., 1 Male and 1 Female; India: Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, Vedal; 14. viii. 2014, Coll.: D. Vimala & Party. 1 ex., 7 Male and 2 Female; India: Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, Kalpattu; 17. viii. 2014; Coll.: D. Vimala & Party.

Diagnostic characters:

Head slightly, if at all, longer than the pronotum, and often shorter. Green; head and pronotum with 2 or 3 pale pink bands on each side; tegmina with two broad pink longitudinal bands, between which is often a whitish line, generally broken into long spots, bordered with blackish; wings hyaline. Lateral carinae of pronotum edged within with a black line.

Distribution:

India: Tamil Nadu. **Elsewhere:** Africa and Nepal.

6. *Acrida turritac* (Linnaeus, 1758)

1758. *Gryllus (Acrida) turritus*

Linnaeus, *Systema Naturae per Regna tria naturae* (10th ed.) 1:427.

1876. *Acrida turrita* Bolívar, *An. Soc. Espan. Hist. Nat.* 5:308-309.

1983. *Acrida turrita* Marshall, *Zool. J. Linn. Soc.* 78(4):393.

2009. *Acrida turrita* Massa, *Jour. Orth. Res.* 18(1):82.

Materials Examined:

1 ex., 1 male and 1 Female; India: Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, Kalpattu; 17. viii. 2014; Coll.: D. Vimala & Party. 2 exs., 1 male and 1 Female; India: Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, Pondur; 18. viii. 2014; Coll.: D. Vimala & Party.

Diagnostic characters:

Green; tegmina long, narrow and pointed, extending when closed beyond the abdomen; head slender, longer than the pronotum by the length of the fastigium in front of the eyes; wings hyaline, pointed at the extremity.

Distribution:

India: Tamil Nadu. **Elsewhere:** Africa, Asia and South Europe.

Remarks: It is a pest of Paddy.

Tribe Epacromiini Brunner von Wattenwyl, 1893

Genus Aiolopus Fieber, 1853

7. *Aiolopus simulatrix simulatrix* (Walker, 1870)

1870. *Epacromia simulatrix* Walker, *Catalogue of the Specimens of Dermaptera Saltatoria in the Collection of the British Museum* 4:773.

1910. *Acrotylus simulatrix* Kirby, *A Synonymic Catalogue of Orthoptera* (Orthoptera Saltatoria, Locustidae vel Acridiidae) 3(2):267.

1914. *Aiolopus tamulus* Kirby, *Fauna of British India, including Ceylon and Burma. Orthoptera* (Acrididae) 122.

1917. *Aeolopus tamulus* Bolívar, *Rev. Real Acad. Cienc. Exact., Fisic. Natur.* 16:382.

1968. *Aiolopus simulatrix simulatrix* Hollis, *Bull. Br. Mus. (Nat. Hist.) Ent.* 22(7):320.

2012. *Aiolopus simulatrix* Nayeem & Usmani, *Munis Entomology & Zoology* 7(1):407.

Materials Examined:

1 ex., India : Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, Kalpattu; 17. viii. 2014, D. Vimala & Party. 1 ex., India : Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, Arcot; 19. viii. 2014, D. Vimala & Party.

Diagnostic characters:

Integument more strongly rugulose. Antenna as long as combined lengths of head and pronotum with twenty-two to twenty-four segments. Fastigium of vertex pentagonal, slightly longer than wide, moderately concave with well defined margins, forward angle narrowly rounded; fastigial foveolae rectangular, shallow, coarsely pitted, with moderately well-defined margins, lower margin often very weak; frontal ridge wide, coarsely and densely pitted, with parallel margins along most of length but narrowing strongly just below fastigium. Eye oval, about one and half times as high as wide and almost twice as high as length of subocular groove. Pronotum relatively narrow; prozona cylindrical above, with very slight median constriction; metazona rather flat, with obtuse angular posterior margin; median longitudinal carina stronger in prozona than in metazona; lateral plate of pronotum higher than wide; mesosternal interspace wider than long, trapezoid, slightly widening posteriorly. Tegmen relatively long.

Hind femur broad; hind tibia shorter than hind femur, with none outer and ten inner spines, inner apical spurs slightly less than twice as long as outer pair; arolium almost half length of claw. Phallic complex with zygoma of cingulum with small dorsal processes and short apodemes; basal valves of penis with small lateral expansions which are not recurved posteriorly.

Distribution: India: Tamil Nadu. **Elsewhere:** Ethiopia, French Somaliland, Kenya, Somalia, Sudan and Tanzania.

8. *Aiolopus thalassinus tamulus* (Fabricius, 1798)

1798. *Gryllus tamulus* Fabricius, *Supplementum Entomologiae Systematicae Suppl.* 195.

1902. *Epacromia tamulus* Bolívar, *Ann. Soc. ent. Fr.* 70:600.

1902. *Aiolopus tamulus* Rehn, *Proc. Acad. Nat. Sci. Philad.* 54:631.

1968. *Aiolopus thalassinus tamulus* Hollis, *Bull. Br. Mus. (Nat. Hist.) Ent.* 22(7):347.

2013. *Aiolopus thalassinus tumulus* Tan, Ngiam, Rifqi bin Ismail & Ibrahim, *Nature in Singapore* 6:220.

Materials Examined:

1 ex., Female; India: Tamil Nadu; Kanchipuram district, Kalpattu; 17. viii. 2014, Coll.: D. Vimala & Party. 2 exs., 2 Female; India: Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, Pondur; 18. viii. 2014; Coll.: D. Vimala & Party.

Diagnostic characters:

Fastigium with forward angle more acute; fastigial foveolae narrowing more strongly anteriorly, frontal ridge flat and continually narrowing upwards; or weakly sulcate and with weak lateral carinae, and junction with fastigium more angular; pronotum with “shoulders” of prozona more parallel in prozona and sometimes even with very weak lateral carinae in prozona; posterior margin of pronotum more rounded. Phallic complex with basal valves of penis less expanded laterally and not recurved. General colouration differs in that Ochraceous or green stripe along costal area of tegmen is usually complete; external area of hind femur without oblique fasciae; hind tibia with red colouration in apical third only or not at all,

and broadly separated from median black band by broad bluish-grey band.

Distribution:

India: Andaman and Nicobar Islands, Bihar, Delhi, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu and West Bengal. **Elsewhere:** Australia, Borneo, Brunei, China, Hainan, Japan, Java and Myanmar.

9. *Trilophidia annulata* (Thunberg, 1815)

1815. *Gryllus annulatus* Thunberg, *Mem. Acad. Imp. Sci. St. Peterburg* 5:234.

1902. *Trilophidia annulata* Bolívar, *Ann. Soc. ent. Fr.* 70:604.

2012. *Trilophidia annulata* Nayeem & Usmani, *Munis Entomology & Zoology* 7(1):406.

Materials Examined:

1ex., India: Tamil Nadu; Kanchipuram district, Vedal; 14. viii. 2014, Coll.: D. Vimala & Party.

Diagnostic characters:

Brown or grey, with black markings, pubescent beneath. Antennae slightly thickened, pale at the base. Pronotum rugose, with a high median carina, forming two teeth in front, and with lateral carinae. Tegmina grey, sometimes with two indistinct brown bands, the extremity brownish hyaline; wings yellow at the base, and brown or black beyond. Hind femora pale outside, spotted above with brown, inside black, with a pale band before the extremity; hind tibiae brown with a pale band towards the base and with a slight pale band beyond the middle; spines pale at the base.

Distribution:

India: Andhra Pradesh, Bihar, Goa, Karnataka, Kerala, Maharashtra, Madhya Pradesh, Odisha and Tamil Nadu. **Elsewhere:** China, Japan, Korea, Mongolia, North Borneo, Pakistan and Sri Lanka.

Subfamily **OXYINAE**

Genus *Oxya* Serville, 1831

10. *Oxya fuscovittata* (Marschall, 1836)

1836. *Gryllus fuscovittatus* Marchall, *Ann. Wien. Mus. Vienna*, 1(2): 211.

1912. *Oxya turanica* Uvarov, *Trudy Russk. Entomol. Obshch.* 40(3): 28.

1925. *Oxya oryzivora* Willemse, *Tidjschr. Ent.*, 68: 25.

1969. *Oxya fuscovittata* Tandon & Shishodia, *Oriental Ins.*, 3(3): 266.

2009. *Oxya fuscovittata* Prabakar, *Fauna of Tamil Nadu, State Fauna Series*, 17, Part 1, Zool. Surv. India: 47.

Materials Examined:

1ex., India : Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, Kalpattu, 17. viii. 2014, Coll.: D. Vimala & Party. 1ex., India : Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, pondur, 18. viii. 2014, Coll.: D. Vimala & Party.

Diagnostic characters:

Integument of the body finely pitted and shiny; females large in size. A black band is running behind the eyes up to the end of the lateral lobes of the pronotum. Anal circus of male compressed and weakly bifurcated. Ventral surface of subgenital plate broad and weakly concave; posterior margin emarginate medially, straight, or with two very small medial spines.

Distribution:

India : Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Himachal Pradesh, Jammu & Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Nagaland, Odisha, Rajasthan, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal. **Elsewhere:** Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Nepal, Pakistan and USSR (South West).

Remarks: This species is associated with paddy fields.

Subfamily **EYPREPOCNEMIDINAE** Brunner Von Wattenwyl, 1893

Tribe **Eyprepocnemidini** Brunner Von Wattenwyl, 1893

Genus *Eyprepocnemis* Fieber, 1853

11. *Eyprepocnemis alacris alacris* (Serville, 1839)

1839. *Acridium alacre* Serville, *Ins. Orth.*, p. 682.

1859. *Acrydium deponens*, Walker, *Ann. Nat. Hist.*, (3) iv, p.222.
1870. *Heteracris rudis*, Walker, *Cat. Derm. Salt. Brit. Mus.*, **4**, p.662, 664.
1902. *Euprepocnemis plorans*, var. *intermedia*, Bolivar, *Ann. Soc. Ent. France*, lxx, p.630.
1914. *Eyprepocnemis alacris*, Kirby, *Faun. Brit. India, Orth.*: 267.
1958. *Eyprepocnemis alacris alacris*, Dirsh, *Proc. R. Ent. Soc. Lond.*, (B) 27(3-4):40.
2009. *Eyprepocnemis alacris alacris*, Prabakar, *Fauna of Tamil Nadu, State Fauna Series*, **17**, Part 1, Zool. Surv. India: 48.
- Afghanistan, Bangladesh, Iran, Iraq, Pakistan and Sri Lanka.

12. *Gryllotalpa africana africana* Palisot de Beauvois, 1805

1805. *Gryllotalpa africana* Palisot de Beauvois, *Insects recueillis en Afrique et en Amérique, Orthopt.* 229.
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2005. *Gryllotalpa africana* Picker, M., Griffiths & Weaving, *Field Guide to Insects of Southern Africa* 88.
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Materials Examined:

1ex., India: Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, Vedal; 14. viii. 2014, Coll.: D. Vimala & Party. 1ex., India: Tamil Nadu; Kanchipuram district, Kalpattu; 17. viii. 2014, Coll.: D. Vimala & Party. 3exs., 1 Male and 3 Females; India: Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, Pondur; 18. viii. 2014; Coll.: D. Vimala & Party.

Diagnostic characters:

Body slightly larger than the medium in size. Fastigium of vertex a little concave, with a low apical carinula, separating it from frontal ridge. Antennae filiform, as long as the head and pronotum together. Dorsum of pronotum flat. Pronotum above with a characteristic narrow dark spot; lateral carinae of pronotum converging forwards; prozona about as long as metazoan; elytra with numerous brown spots; dark spots present on the wings. Posterior femora with a long and black streak. Posterior tibiae bluish-grey with two whitish rings at the base and reddish at apex; male circus gradually narrowing towards apex, incurved and down curved.

Distribution:

India : Andhra Pradesh, Arunachal Pradesh, Assam, Bihar, Chhattisgarh, Delhi, Goa, Haryana, Himachal Pradesh, Karnataka, Kerala, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Manipur, Meghalaya, Odisha, Punjab, Rajasthan, Sikkim, Tamil Nadu, Tripura, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal. **Elsewhere:**

Materials Examined:

1 ex., Male; India: Tamil Nadu, Kanchipuram district, Arcot; 19. viii. 2014, Coll.: D. Vimala & Party.

Diagnostic characters:

Head darker; pronotum and legs plain brown never rufous. Ocelli oval. Pronotum well-rounded behind; anterior margin feebly concave; inferior margin of the lateral lobes rather strongly sinuated. Anterior femora short and stout, with feebly sinuated inferior margin; tibial dactyls wide and rather short, touching at base. Posterior tibiae with internal margin armed with 4 spines; posterior tarsi long and rather slender. Discoidal cell of elytra narrow, twice as long as wide at base; a second cell between the diagonal vein and the first chord almost as large as the discoidal. Wings very long. Teeth in the stridulatory file more widely spaced in the centre than at ends. Genitalia very large, with long ventral processes.

Distribution:

India: Assam, Bihar, Jammu and Kashmir, Karnataka, Kerala, Meghalaya, Odisha,

Puducherry, Punjab, Tamil Nadu, Uttarakhand, Uttar Pradesh and West Bengal. **Elsewhere:** Bhutan, Myanmar, Malaysia, Nepal, Pakistan, Singapore and Sri Lanka.

CONCLUSION

The paper presents the checklist and diagnostic characters of orthoptera of Kanchipuram district along with their known distribution which includes 12 species/subspecies of belonging to 9 genera under 2 Suborder, 3 Superfamilies, 3 families and 7 subfamilies.

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